

INCLUSION EDUCATION, A STUDY AND CRITICAL ANALYSIS WITH THE DIMENSIONS OF INCLUSION INDEX IN SMPN 28 SURABAYA

(Pendidikan Inklusi, Sebuah Telaah dan Analisis Kritis Dengan Dimensi Indeks Inklusi di SMPN 28 Surabaya)

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Abstract— *Inclusive education has now begun to develop in many schools in Indonesia, especially in Surabaya. Inclusive education is the development of education that can serve all characters of students without discrimination in Indonesia. The general objective of this study is to describe and analyze the management of inclusive education in SMP Negeri 28 Surabaya to measure the quality of schools in managing inclusive education using the inclusive index dimension. Management of the organizers of inclusive schools is based on appointments from the central government which are forwarded to the Surabaya City government. Management of identification and assessment of students is done at the beginning of the students entering, the assessment results are carried out to determine the abilities, weaknesses and needs of special needs students, which will determine the making of learning curriculum modification programs covering aspects of objectives, sources, materials, media, schedules, and assessment. Changes in curriculum modification are intended so that students with special needs can be properly served in accordance with the characteristics and needs of each student. From the curriculum modification will produce individual learning programs. management of learning is carried out collaboratively between subject teachers, GPK, BK teachers, and homeroom teachers to obtain optimal learning conditions. Management of assessment takes into account the circumstances of special needs students and regular students.*

Keywords— *School for Providing Inclusive Education; Management of Inclusive Education; Students with special needs;*

1. Introduction

Based on the 1945 Constitution Article 31 paragraph 1 and Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, it can be concluded that the state provides full guarantees to children with special needs to obtain quality education services. This shows that children with special needs or extraordinary children have the right to have the same opportunities as other children in education.

Research on education for students with disabilities has become more focused, especially in Article 32 paragraph 1 stated that special education is education for students who have a level of difficulty in following the learning process because of physical, emotional, mental, social, and / or having abnormalities. intelligence potential and special talent. However, with the opinion that there is no strong empirical evidence that the Extraordinary School is the only best system for the education of special needs students, the cost of administering Extraordinary Schools is far more expensive than with regular schools, many special needs students live in regions unable to attend Special Schools because of the far and / or unreachable costs, the Extraordinary School is a school that separates students from real social life, while inclusive schools are more 'uniting' students with real life, many evidence in regular schools there are special needs students who do not get

appropriate services, (6) the implementation of special schools implies labeling of 'disabled' students that can cause lifelong stigma so parents do not want to send their children to special schools, and through inklu education sif there can be a process of educating the public to appreciate the difference (Fitriyah, 2017), so that opinion strongly supports that inclusive education is an effort to accelerate the fulfillment of the right to education for each student.

Inclusive education which is often called inclusive or often called inclusive education is education based on the spirit to provide education services to every citizen. The inclusive education model is the latest development of the education model for Children with Special Needs which was formally affirmed in Salamanca's 1994 statement at the World Conference on Disabled Education that "The fundamental principles of inclusive education are: as long as possible, all children should learn together regardless of difficulties or the differences that might exist in them. "

Likewise the development of inclusive education in Indonesia has begun to develop in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture No. 70 of 2009 concerning inclusive education, article 1). Stating that inclusive education is a system of education that provides opportunities for all students who have abnormalities and have the potential of intelligence and /

or special talents to participate in education or learning in an educational environment together with students in general.

Along with some of the laws and regulations above, the Surabaya City Government supports Permendiknas 70/2009, among others by appointing 51 Public Elementary Schools and 20 Junior High Schools as providers of inclusive education by the Surabaya City Education Agency. All of the schools designated by the Surabaya City Education Agency have almost all received training on the management of inclusive education in shaping inclusive schools in schools and inclusive policy-based learning processes carried out in an inclusive manner.

Based on preliminary observations on the management of inclusive education in Surabaya, the problems that arise regarding the implementation of inclusive schools come from teachers, students, parents, schools, communities, the government, lack of facilities and infrastructure, and lack of cooperation from various parties. These problems have an impact on the lack of inclusive school implementation. Solving problems about inclusive education can be found in bright spots if there is in-depth research on the implementation of inclusive, especially in schools that have been culturally inclusive. The follow-up to addressing the issue of inclusive education requires effective management or management.

According to Ainscow (2006) and Carrington & Macarthur (2012) to measure the quality of schools in managing inclusive education can use the inclusive index dimension. The dimension of the inclusive index is a framework of values that underlies the actions needed to move towards a more inclusive society. The values of the school community influence policies and practices at school. Success in applying the dimensions of the inclusion index is seen from how an identity and all can work well and support each other. The dimensions of the inclusion index cover three dimensions, namely creating an inclusive culture, generating inclusive policies, and formulating inclusive implementation. Each dimension has two subdimensions, and each subdimension includes several indicators.

This study aims to examine the key aspects of education services for all including inclusive students held in regular schools on an inclusive basis, there are two reasons research is considered important, firstly the development of the democratization process in the field of education in Indonesia so that education is a right that must be obtained by every member of the community without discrimination. Second, in realizing inclusive education, it is still relatively new, it requires more in-depth study to achieve effective and quality services.

In addition, there is substantial uniqueness in the management of inclusive education at SMPN 28 Surabaya. In schools this provider of inclusive education serves students who have normal academic abilities (without having special needs) and students who have special needs with various characters in the same learning environment, while most teachers who serve special needs students with no from special education. It also becomes interesting to study because schools need to change all dimensions of the education process in the school which includes cultural dimensions, policy dimensions and dimensions of learning practice.

2. Method

The method used in this study is descriptive analysis with an approach carried out by collecting data from conducting case

studies in the field by conducting observations and interviews at SMP Negeri 28 Surabaya as schools providing inclusive education to view data empirically.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the exposure of the research findings, an overall picture of the management of inclusive education schools in Surabaya 28 Public Junior High School was obtained. For school readiness in providing opportunities for all students to participate in learning together, SMPN 28 Surabaya has been able to implement it. This can be seen from the diversity of students who have barriers to studying at SMPN 28 Surabaya and almost all classes have students with special needs who study together with other regular students. The following are data from students from year to year at SMPN 28 Surabaya.

Table 1: Student Data Table

Th. Ajaran	Jml Pendaftar (Cln Siswa Baru)	Kelas VII		Kelas VIII		Kelas IX		Jumlah (Kls. VII + VIII + IX)	
		Jml Siswa	Ro mb el	Jml Siswa	Rom bel	Jml Siswa	Romb el	Sisw a	Romb el
2009/2010	1040	298	8	279	10	317	8	994	26
2010/2011	1024	302	8	303	8	374	10	979	26
2011/2012	1000	379	10	301	8	300	8	980	26
2012/2013	1492	304	8	372	10	293	8	969	26
2013/2014	922	379	10	300	8	369	10	1048	28
2014/2015	1047	378	10	371	10	298	8	1047	28
2015/2016	644	382	10	372	10	370	10	1124	30
2016/2017	750	378	10	379	10	371	10	1128	30
2017/2018	600	375	10	378	10	378	10	1131	30
2018/2019	600	456	11	374	10	377	10	1207	31

Educators and educators at 28th Junior High School in Surabaya, namely 1 headmaster, 58 teachers teaching subjects, 4 special assistant teachers consisting of 2 psychologists and 2 special education graduates, and 19 education staff including 8 administrative staff, 1 library person, 1 UKS guard, 5 cleaning guards, and 4 security guards.

The facilities and infrastructure available at SMPN 28 Surabaya are complete, all equipment that supports the progress of students who have various kinds of obstacles have been provided in the therapy room and in the source room.

Ainscow (2006) states that in compiling school policies it can encourage the participation of children and practitioners from the time they first join school by minimizing exclusive pressure and respect for diversity through a school framework.

The results of this study found that the management and development of an inclusive culture in schools providing inclusive education in SMPN 28 Surabaya was based on an inclusive education policy by the central government which was followed up by the Surabaya City government. Based on the appointment, the personnel of inclusive education in Surabaya believed and committed to become an inclusive school to serve special needs students and regular students. Schools internally make policies that support this education service, there is no discrimination for students who have a diversity of characteristics according to their constraints.

Referring to Booth T, (2006) there are two factors that will influence success and failure in the implementation of inclusive education policies, including developing schools for all and supporting differences in values. Thus, it can be concluded that the success factor of the implementation of inclusive education at 28th Junior High School in Surabaya is that the school personnel administering inclusive education studied have the confidence to succeed in carrying out their duties, commitment in carrying out mandates (tasks) from the state, and enthusiasm to assist community education (including children with special needs).

A. Management of children's identification and assessment special needs in inclusive education school

According to Smith (2012), schools providing inclusive education need to carry out accurate identification and assessment by trained personnel and / or professionals in their fields to develop an appropriate and objective education program. The results of this study found that the assessment of the individual characteristics of students in schools providing inclusive education in SMPN 28 Surabaya was conducted in conjunction with New Student Admission activities.

According to Stainback & Stainback (in Irdamurni & Rahmiati, 2017, p. 2) inclusive schools are schools that accommodate all students in the same class. This school provides education programs that are feasible, challenging, but in accordance with the abilities and needs of students as well as the assistance and support that teachers can provide so that children succeed. In the process of identification and assessment of special needs students are asked to provide health reports, and take some basic ability tests. While parents of students are asked for information or health records of the students concerned as an initial description in determining the school program. If the school knows the initial data of students it can prepare facilities or facilities and infrastructure that are in the school, so that students get the right service.

The procedure for identifying activities in this school starts with the acceptance of new students. After students were found to be suspected of having Children with Special Needs, their parents were asked to consult with a psychologist to determine the child's IQ then the child was grouped and placed in the class evenly. The next step is for these two experts to conduct pre-academic assessments, especially their motoric and they analyze the results, then make a learning program for each child with special needs and the results are submitted to the guardian who has children with special needs.

Furthermore, the schools providing inclusive education at 28th Junior High School in Surabaya, have obtained data on students with special needs in the field of opportunity. In the placement of students in class involving homeroom and assessment team identification. The identification team consists of class teachers, GPK, experts (psychologists, specialists who are related to disability) and collect information on identification instruments of special students from experts.

Consideration of placement of students with special needs in inclusive classrooms, by schools providing inclusive education at 28 Surabaya Junior High Schools from the assessment results. Assessment analysis obtained data that describes the abilities, weaknesses, and needs of students. Management of students after placement is the responsibility of

the homeroom teacher. The class in the inclusive class is a facilitator in the classroom so special needs students can easily mingle, interact and work together with his classmates. Homeroom is also a motivator in the learning process that takes place in the classroom. However, also as a medium in the learning process, where the homeroom monitors students with special needs and meets the needs needed by students with special needs.

Furthermore, students who have been placed in inclusive classes become the responsibility of homeroom teachers. Classes work together and collaborate with GPK in assessment and identification of students, as well as in the preparation of Individual Learning Programs, so that ABK students get services according to their abilities.

B. Management of curriculum modification or development in inclusive education school

In accordance with the statement of Churchill R, et al (2011), that schools providing inclusive education must be able to develop curricula according to the level, development, and characteristics of students so that graduates have the competencies for life skills.

The statement supports the findings of this study which shows that in Surabaya's inclusive education provider schools, the parties involved in the development team covered the modifications consisting of class teachers, special education teachers, and other administrators in charge of the curriculum. They collaborate in formulating a curriculum that is friendly to students so that children's needs can be fulfilled. In essence, the curriculum is prepared by taking care of the conditions of the students.

The purpose of curriculum modification or development is to (1) Help students develop their potential and overcome barriers to learning that are experienced to the maximum extent possible in inclusive school settings. (2) Helping teachers and parents to develop educational programs for special needs students both held at school and at home. (3) Become a guideline for schools, and the community in developing, assessing and perfecting inclusive education programs.

Some considerations that are used as the basis for curriculum modification, in schools that provide inclusive education are to be adjusted to the abilities of students. For example, for gifted students, teachers can modify it by adding curriculum that is above the curriculum that should be applied in class, or by giving advice. For students with intellectual disabilities, the teacher decreases the curriculum. That is, when typical students in the class use the curriculum that is supposed to, but on students with intellectual barriers by lowering the learning material.

The modified curriculum in schools providing inclusive education in SMPN 28 Surabaya is the result of adjusting the curriculum standards of educational units with the ability of special needs students. Students with special needs need modification of the curriculum tailored to the needs of students based on specific needs or conditions. It has. Thus, both students who do not have intellectual barriers or students who are accompanied by intellectual barriers, both require curriculum modification. Modification of the curriculum concerns the allocation of time, curriculum content / material, teaching and

learning processes, learning infrastructure, learning environment, and classroom management.

Related to the Individual Learning Program Curriculum, in schools providing inclusive education at 28th Junior High School in Surabaya, it is a learning program for individual students who are tailored to their own abilities, methods, and speed. With the help of the Individual Learning Program, individual learners can gradually show an increase in learning abilities through specific approaches, concerns, ways and actions.

The preparation, implementation, and assessment of the Individual Learning Program applies the principle of cooperation, involving: the principal, parents of students, subject matter teachers and special guidance teachers (GPK). In the implementation of the PPI, students learn together in one class, but the material is different according to the ability of students or in the learning resource space accompanied by GPK.

Stages of Individual Learning Program preparation, namely (1) studying the profile of students, (2) determining the abilities of the most basic learners and need to be improved, (3) determining the strengths and weaknesses of students in the subject of certain subjects, (4) making general goals (basic competencies), (5) making specific goals (indicators), (6) compiling Teaching and Learning Activities (material, media, methods, evaluations), and (7) determining the time allocation, place, and parties involved.

In relation to the development of a modified curriculum, inclusive schools have problems because the inclusion school curriculum needs to be developed specifically according to the characteristics of learners (Praptiningrum, 2010). In addition, Sunaryo (2009) found problems related to the inclusive curriculum, namely (1) teachers tend to still experience difficulties in formulating flexible curriculum, and in determining goals, material, and learning methods, (2) there are still practices that target errors. the curriculum of special needs students is the same as other students as well as the assumption that disabled students do not have sufficient ability to master learning material, (3) limited school facilities, so that the implementation of learning has not used diverse media, resources, and environments according to the needs of the child, (4) there is no clear guidance on the assessment system that has not used a flexible and diverse approach, and (5) there is still a perception that the learning outcomes assessment system of students with special needs is the same as other regular students, so the perception is that they do not show meaningful learning progress.

In general, it can be concluded that the management and development of an inclusive curriculum are as follows. The inclusive school development team or the teacher changes the national curriculum into a modified curriculum based on the characteristics and needs of the students. Modified national curricula at inclusive schools are important concerning aspects of objectives, sources, materials, media, schedules, and assessments. Teachers who teach in inclusive classes prepare themselves by arranging individual learning programs by paying attention to the characteristics and needs of students. Management of schools providing inclusive education if they form a special team of inclusive education developers tasked with modifying the curriculum and preparing teachers, the

curriculum according to the characteristics, individual needs, and development of students.

C. Management of inclusive learning practices in inclusive education schools

According to Olsen (2003) for children who need special education services provided continuous support in the form of minimal assistance in the regular class. For learning given individually according to their needs. Whereas Foreman (1997) states that the placement of special needs students in the regular class does not guarantee their integrity, but it is important to do this to prepare regular teachers and students in the class so they can accept and respect those students with special needs.

In the learning process students with special needs are flexible moving from one form of service to another form of service, such as: (a) full regular class form, (b) regular class form with cluster form, (c) regular class form with pull out, (d) regular class forms with clusters and pull outs, (e) special class forms with various integration, (f) full special class forms in regular schools (Ermawati, 2008).

In class management, according to Deno (in Hermanto, 2010) there are seven management models of inclusive classes with different hierarchies, namely: (1) full ordinary class, (2) ordinary class with additional guidance inside, (3) ordinary class with additional outside the classroom, (4) special classes with opportunities to join in ordinary classes, (5) full special classes, (6) special schools, and (7) boarding schools. In classroom management, which is prioritized creates an effective and pleasant learning atmosphere and motivates students to develop their competencies optimally.

In the inclusion class there is a homeroom accompanied by GPK and other supporters to meet the learning needs of all good students whose special needs and regular learners. At SMPN 28 Surabaya, GPK comes from teachers who have the expertise to handle special needs students who also work with psychologists. The homeroom teacher shares responsibility with GPK and other supporters to teach all students.

In providing services to special needs students and regular students in one class, there are several things that need to be considered by teachers and homeroom teachers. For example, teachers use an individual and classical approach, giving time individually if students have not been able to take part in classical activities. The teacher shapes behavior and guides academics. Teachers are required to be creative in teaching using interesting media. Teachers need to give discussion time, provide learning opportunities, and conduct evaluations. Therefore, the teacher discusses with the homeroom teacher about the conditions of the students, the Individual Learning Program of the students, and when giving the agreed work.

Management of inclusive learning practices if done collaboratively between subject teachers, GPK, BK teachers, and trained homerooms, the students who follow learning can develop optimally according to their potential and characteristics.

D. Management of assessment in inclusive education school

Carrington (2014) states that in the dimensions of inclusive implementation practices include sub-dimensions of overall learning implementation, and mobilizing resources, it is

indicated that one of them is the evaluation that contributes to the achievements of all students, class discipline based on mutual feelings respect, teachers design, teach, review in teamwork.

Based on the results of research findings on the management and development of inclusive assessments in SMPN 28 Surabaya, special needs students who have followed the Learning can be assessed by paying attention to the situation of students in special and regular needs. Regular students, standards for assessing the achievement of their competencies, use competency standards. While students with special needs, the standard of assessment of achievement of competence is the same as that of regular students but the method and weight of the assessment are flexible in accordance with the characteristics of the students. The students do not complete or the achievement of competence is less than the maximum value, must follow remedial learning a maximum of 3 times to achieve the standard value. For students with special needs who complete or reach standard values according to their basic abilities. For students with special needs, the criteria get special treatment in the form of an increase in class or graduation based on chronological age. The management of inclusive student competency assessment is tailored to the characteristics of students, that special needs students who have lower average standard abilities are based on chronological age, and regular students use standardized values to achieve national curriculum competencies.

E. Inclusive culture management in inclusive education school

Ainscow (2006) and Carrington & Macarthur (2012), state that schools create a culture of inclusion, namely by building inclusive communities, and creating inclusive values. Indications that the school builds community is the existence of behavior as follows: everyone feels accepted, the students help each other, the teachers work together with each other, the teachers and students treat each other with respect, there is a partnership between teachers and parents / guardians, teachers and the government work together well, and all communities are involved in the school. As for schools, creating inclusive values, with the following behaviors, there are high expectations for all students, teachers, the government, students and parents / guardians sharing the philosophy of inclusion, the students have the same values, teachers and students treat one each other as human beings and as their role holders, teachers try to eliminate barriers to learning and participation in all aspects of the school, and schools struggle to minimize all forms of discrimination.

School efforts for providers of inclusive education at 28th Junior High School in Surabaya, in improving inclusion culture, can be seen in self-development and extracurricular programs. Self-development is an activity that aims to provide opportunities for students to develop and express themselves according to their needs, talents, interests, each student in accordance with the conditions of the school. Self-development activities Inclusive schools in Surabaya, including guidance and counseling services, and civilizing spiritual attitudes and social attitude.

Civilization that supports inclusion education, in Surabaya inclusive school organizers also held habituation (1) flag ceremonies, (2) incidental flag ceremonies (National Great Results), (3) religious activities, (4) joint prayer, (5) singing national songs and regional songs, (6) literacy programs, (7)

social care, and (8) environmental care activities / adi wiyata. This civilizing activity is held on a scheduled basis.

Extracurricular activities are fostered by teachers who have qualifications in their fields, followed by special and regular students. Compulsory extracurricular in inclusive organizers of Surabaya as inclusive schools is scouting. While extracurricular activities are not compulsory in the fields of sports, paskibra, PMR, peer counselors, youth scientific work, arts, and religion. To increase inclusive civilization, inclusive school organizers Surabaya sets the days for special activities, including (1) Introduction to the School Environment, and (2) Mid-term activities in the form of outside-class learning held per semester.

The development of an inclusive school organizers in SMPN 28 Surabaya in the future as an inclusive school is carried out with inclusive culture, managerial improvement, and increasing stakeholder support. Inclusive civilization includes activities related to special and regular learners for mutual tolerance and social equality (mutual respect, without discrimination). Managerial reform is directed at increasing teacher attitudes and abilities through consultation with inclusive and disability experts. Physical development and the school environment continue to be directed towards accessibility and friendliness of students with special needs. Stakeholder support continues to be made. Support from the Surabaya City government and the Surabaya City Education Office in the form of policies and funding for inclusive schools continues to be supported. School committee support for school policies is maintained. Parental support to entrust their children to study in other inclusive organizers of Surabaya is capital that needs to be maintained. Parental support is evident when they feel the success and behavior of their son is getting better.

The results of this study are consistent with the opinion that public perceptions and education stakeholders assume that students with special needs are disabled and cannot be educated together with normal children. From these conditions the impact on the initiative of stakeholders and the community is still partial to the implementation of inclusive education. Every student has a unique and different. They have different abilities, learn with different styles, and different stages of development. Schools need to be inclusive, learning-friendly, and a barrier-free environment. Every school and community throughout the world needs to facilitate so that students are able to develop their full academic, social, emotional and physical potential.

4. Conclusion

Schools providing inclusive education at 28th Junior High School in Surabaya carry out inclusive education based on government appointments. Then the school establishes an inclusive school development team to develop inclusive school development policies and programs. Schools that provide inclusive education where there are Children with Special Needs, so teachers are required to carry out identification and assessment independently and the results can be used as the basis for making learning programs tailored to the needs of the child.

The success of SMPN 28 Surabaya as a school providing inclusive education based on preliminary observations was due to effective and efficient management in the application of the inclusive index dimension (Carrington & Macarthur 2012). Achievement of successful school management in implementing effective and quality inclusive education, namely by the

formulation of policies in the formation of inclusive education development teams, school program plans and the availability of budgets and facilities that support the strengthening of inclusive culture, assessment process assessment and individual learning programs, the implementation of curriculum modification and learning practices and assessments that strengthen the formation of an inclusive culture.

Identification and assessment is carried out at the beginning of the students entering the school to prepare all types of services tailored to the needs of students. From the results of the assessment the teacher can create a learning program that requires changes to the national curriculum into a modified curriculum. Changes to the curriculum are based on the characteristics and needs of students. Modification of the curriculum concerns aspects of objectives, sources, materials, media, schedules, and assessments. For teachers who teach in inclusive classes, they must prepare themselves by compiling individual learning programs in accordance with the results of student assessment.

Learning practices at inclusive host schools in SMPN 28 Surabaya, both special and regular students, are conducted collaboratively between subject teachers, special guidance teachers (GPK), counseling teachers, and homeroom teachers. Management of inclusive learning practices if done collaboratively between subject teachers, GPK, counseling teachers, and homeroom teachers, the students who take part in learning can develop optimally according to the optimal according to their potential and characteristics.

To measure the achievement of the competency standards of inclusive students who have participated in the teaching and learning process an assessment is carried out by drawing on the service characteristics of students. For regular students, the standard of achievement of competency achievement uses the maximum competency standard. Whereas students with special needs, standards for assessment of achievement of competence are flexible in accordance with the characteristics of students. For students with special needs, the increase in class or graduation marks get special treatment, which is based on chronological age. And for regular participants using standard competencies to achieve national curriculum competencies.

The development of schools providing inclusive education can be more effective and efficient by providing training on inclusive education in advance to school personnel. Parents of students and communities who get socialization and education about inclusive education the level of acceptance and support for schools increases. Inclusive civilization of schools providing inclusive education is carried out through classroom learning, scouting activities, self-development and extracurricular activities (sports, arts, and religion) can be followed by all students according to their interests

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